

CONSUMER BEHAVIOR ON THE INTERNET: METHODOLOGY, TOOLS AND CURRENT TRENDS

FAWZIEH MOHAMMED MASA'D¹, NASIEM MOHAMMED ALYAMI², HASSAN ALI AL-
ABABNEH³, OLGA POPOVA⁴, NATALIYA MASLOVA⁵, OLEKSANDR TYSHKO⁶

¹ Doctor of Human Resources Management, Assistant Professor of the Department of Human Resources Management Jadara University, Irbid 21110, Jordan

² Doctor of Marketing, Associate Professor of the Department of Marketing and E-Commerce, Faculty of Business Administration, Najran University, Saudi Arabia

³ Doctor of Marketing, Associate Professor, Department of Electronic Marketing and Social Media, Zarqa University, Jordan

⁴ Doctor of Science Economics, Professor, Vice Rector for Scientific Affairs, Donetsk National Technical University, Ukraine

⁵ PhD in Technical Sciences, Associate Professor, Department of Applied Mathematics and Informatics, Donetsk National Technical University, Ukraine

⁶ Doctoral Student (Economics) Department of Economics and Humanities, Donetsk National Technical University, Ukraine,

E-mail: ¹fawziehm@jadara.edu.jo, ²nmalyami@nu.edu.sa, ³hassan_ababneh@zu.edu.jo

⁴olha.popova@donntu.edu.ua, ⁵nataliia.maslova@donntu.edu.ua, ⁶oleksandr.tyshko@donntu.edu.ua

ABSTRACT

The key objective of the article is to develop methodological approaches to identifying modern trends in consumer behavior on the Internet. The object of the study is marketing concepts and their transformation under the influence of modern Internet technologies, which are reflected in consumer behavior, which requires study to determine strategic directions and guidelines for marketing. The relevance and necessity of studying this issue is due to the fundamental penetration of technology and the Internet and the impact on consumer behavior, which is a key link in marketing and their transformation should be taken into account in the marketing strategy of modern companies. The main results of the study are characterized by the following: the main types of consumer behavior models are systematized, which made it possible to highlight their features, which will take into account all their specifics when forming a marketing strategy for modern companies; the key stages of developing marketing concepts are structured and the role of consumers in each of them is argued; The trends of consumer behavior on the Internet are conceptualized from the point of view of socio-demographic and gender characteristics, as well as their propensity to make purchases on the Internet. The presented results of the study made it possible to determine modern trends in consumer behavior based on the developed methodology and tools of economic and statistical analysis of daily marketing models, development of its key tools and assessments of the influx into the behavior of the lull. Practical application of the results will ensure the effectiveness of the formation of marketing policy and strategy, taking into account the developed aspects in terms of studying consumer behavior, which is key in modern marketing under the influence of modern Internet technologies and innovations.

Keywords: *Marketing, Strategy, Model, Consumer Behavior*

1. INTRODUCTION

The intensive development of the processes of globalization and internationalization of the world economy is also accompanied by the rapid development of e-commerce, which leads to the

emergence of new marketing tools aimed at expanding the market and increasing consumer loyalty to goods and services [1]. An actual and demanded direction in the scientific literature is the study of consumer behavior in modern conditions. Since the main factor, accelerating the formation and

development of the information society is the Internet, which has become not only a global means of communication without territorial and national boundaries [2], but also an effective tool for doing business and researching the impact on the audience, there is a conceptual need for a detailed study and development of this topic. It should be noted that global macroeconomic imbalances in the world economy are forcing the top management of companies and organizations to revise their management strategies in order to optimize costs and improve business efficiency [3], which in modern conditions can only be achieved with the help of information and the Internet. The development of information technologies in the world and their application in practice has allowed many manufacturers not only to reduce the costs of promoting and selling products, but also to expand existing and develop new markets, improve management efficiency and purposeful interaction with consumers and other counterparties. Given the above, the study of consumer behavior in the modern realities of doing business, which largely depends on the preferences and moods of consumers, it is necessary to identify key trends in their behavior for further development of a methodology, taking into account the lack of a unified approach and concept in this area. Innovative approaches in the organization of marketing activities are focused on the development and widespread use of modern Internet tools, namely [4]: social networks and popularization of the promotion of their goods and services in social networks [5]; transformation of relations with the end consumer - maximum consideration of the desires and interests of a particular consumer; an individual approach to each consumer, which ensures an increase in customer loyalty and, in turn, requires the development of a methodology for evaluating their behavior. However, given the fact that in the scientific literature there is no single scientific and methodological approach to identifying trends in the transformation of modern marketing models and assessing their impact on consumer behavior, as well as conceptualizing the impact of innovations and Internet technologies on the development of modern marketing tools, substantiates the relevance and necessity in-depth study of this topic [6].

Effective conduct of marketing activities of modern companies cannot be imagined without a strategy based on the analysis and research of the market, consumers and competitors [7]. Based on this, it is important to state that just the study of consumer behavior under the influence of the Internet in modern conditions is relevant and in

demand, which is confirmed by many studies that are in search of optimal approaches to studying the main aspects of consumer behavioral character [8, 9]. However, to ensure the effectiveness of modern business, it is necessary to use innovative technologies that have a significant impact on the consumer and require the development of a methodology for evaluating key behavioral trends that can be applied in the formation of business goals and objectives of companies [10].

The need and relevance of the topic these studies are determined by current trends and the transformation of existing marketing models, which make it necessary to revise the marketing strategies of companies, given that the key role should be given to the consumer, his needs and preferences. It should be noted that with the development of the information society, the Internet is becoming an integral part of the economic processes of market entities. The Internet is turning from a communication channel into an environment for the interaction of market participants, which is characterized by its own characteristics and infrastructure and requires additional research, detailing and identifying key trends and their impact on the development of relations between companies and consumers. Since, in the scientific literature there is no single approach and vision of the modern effective marketing model of the company, which requires a more detailed definition and implementation in methodological approaches to management and the formation of practical recommendations, taking into account the specifics of the company's activities. Activity, its segment, brand and features of interaction with consumers, which makes it possible to highlight the conceptual necessity of these studies and its relevance. There is no doubt that the relevance of studying consumer behavior trends on the Internet is currently beyond doubt, as the digitalization of the economy and everyday life significantly changes the ways in which users interact with goods and services. In the context of the rapid development of technology and the Internet, consumer behavior has become much more diverse and unpredictable. More and more people choose to purchase and service online, which creates new challenges for businesses and marketers. One of the key factors of relevance is the constant growth in the number of Internet users, as well as the expansion of the range of online services and goods. This creates a need for in-depth research into how consumers behave online, what criteria they consider when making purchasing decisions, how often and for what reasons they change their preferences. Studying these aspects is necessary for accurately

predicting consumer behavior and developing effective marketing strategies.

In addition, with the development of technologies such as data analytics, artificial intelligence and machine learning, it has become possible to collect and analyze a huge amount of information about user actions online. These tools allow you to accurately determine patterns in consumer behavior, as well as predict changes in their preferences and requests. An equally important aspect is the impact of changes in the digital environment, such as the emergence of new platforms, changes in legislation or user behavior on social networks. This forces companies to constantly adapt their approaches to sales and advertising. Thus, studying consumer behavior trends on the Internet is becoming not just important, but vital for the successful operation of companies in the digital era.

1.1. Main unresolved research problems

Research into online consumer behavior trends faces a number of challenges that require careful consideration. It is important to consider both methodological and technical aspects of the study, as well as social and ethical factors that affect the accuracy and reliability of the findings.

1. Methodological challenges. One of the key challenges is the selection of appropriate methods for analyzing online consumer behavior. Traditional methods, such as surveys and focus groups, do not always provide accurate results in the context of online user activity, as they cannot fully capture the diversity and dynamism of online behavior. To address this issue, the work will use a combined approach that includes both qualitative and quantitative methods. In particular, big data analysis will be used to more accurately track real user behavior, rather than relying solely on self-reports. The study will also develop new approaches to data analysis that can take into account the dynamic variability of user preferences.

2. Data quality issues. Collecting data on online user behavior is associated with information quality issues. Often, data is incomplete or distorted due to the anonymity of user actions or limitations of the platforms on which information is collected. This problem is solved through the use of data cleaning and processing methods, as well as improving machine learning algorithms to identify patterns even in incomplete data. The work will use an approach to data validation that will minimize the impact of random errors and inaccuracies, as well as increase the accuracy of the results.

3. Privacy and ethics issues. One of the unresolved issues is maintaining user privacy when

collecting and analyzing data. In the context of increasing attention to the protection of personal information, it is necessary to take into account legal requirements and ethical standards. The work will pay special attention to the principles of anonymity and the protection of personal data, which will ensure compliance with user rights and maintain trust in the research results. To solve this problem, data anonymization will be used, which eliminates the possibility of linking them to specific users, as well as the creation of ethical standards that will be applied at all stages of the work.

4. Problems with predicting consumer behavior. The difficulty of predicting user behavior on the Internet is that people's preferences and interests can change under the influence of many factors: economic, social, cultural and technological. This makes predicting long-term behavior quite difficult. To solve this problem, the article will propose a flexible approach to forecasting based on short-term trends and rapid response to changes. The use of machine learning methods will allow more accurate modeling of changes in consumer preferences depending on external factors, such as seasonal fluctuations, marketing campaigns or technological innovations.

5. Social and cultural differences. One of the important problems is the influence of social and cultural factors on user behavior on the Internet. For example, in different countries or regions, consumer preferences can vary greatly, which creates difficulties in developing universal marketing strategies. The paper will propose an approach that takes these differences into account. To do this, users will be segmented by key social and cultural characteristics, which will allow more accurate analysis and forecasting of consumer behavior in different contexts.

1.2. Key research goals and objectives

The aim of the research is to develop methodical approaches to the determination of trends in consumer behavior on the Internet, which will ensure the identification of key needs and preferences of consumers with further consideration and orientation of the company's. This will make it possible to marketing concept to them, will allow to provide an understanding of the need to create a particular product by the company taking into account the preferences and needs of consumers, rapid response to changes in consumer behavior and adjustment of marketing activities, introduction of innovations and Internet technologies in marketing to improve the processes of interaction and study of consumers.

To achieve the goal of the study, the following tasks were set:

- To systematize consumer behavior models in modern conditions;
- substantiate the key stages of development of marketing concepts with arguments for the role of the consumer;
- argue for key methods for analyzing trends in consumer behavior on the Internet based on socio-demographic and gender characteristics, their propensity to purchase using Internet marketing tools;
- To structure consumer behavior trends, to highlight the main types of consumption and their characteristics.

1.3. Novelty of the work and key aspects of solving research problems

Solving problems related to the analysis of consumer behavior on the Internet requires an integrated approach that combines advanced methods and technologies. One of the main problems is the quality of data, since many platforms are limited in their ability to collect accurate and complete information. To solve this problem, the work will use the methodology of economic and statistical analysis, which will ensure higher accuracy of the analysis and will allow identifying key trends. In addition, the integration of various data sources is used, which will compensate for the shortcomings of individual sets.

Another key problem is the instability and dynamism of user behavior. To solve it, a flexible approach to structuring data and arguing key types of consumers based on the contextual attributes of behavior on the Internet, based on the analysis of short-term trends, will be used. This will provide more accurate and prompt forecasts adapted to changes in external factors, such as seasonal fluctuations or changes in the economic situation. The novelty of the work lies in the use of a combination of methods and approaches to the analysis and argumentation of modern trends in consumer behavior on the Internet in the context of marketing and e-commerce strategies of modern companies. This approach allows for more accurate forecasting of consumer behavior on the Internet, as well as taking into account cultural and social differences, which is important for adapting marketing strategies in different countries and regions. Thus, the proposed solutions ensure high efficiency of analysis and forecasting of consumer trends.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The modern development of innovations and information technologies is accompanied by great demand and implementation in all sectors of the world economy. The development of Internet technologies in the modern world is one of the most important strategic tools used in all aspects of human activity to optimize business processes, improve the innovative component of a company's strategy, and improve relationships with the target audience and consumers.

2.1 Theory of development of information technologies and their application in marketing activities

The practical implementation of these technologies opens up wide opportunities for the formation of an effective management system for a modern company using innovative marketing tools for sales promotion, communications, advertising, positioning of goods and services using remote customer service channels, which confirms the relevance of this study and the need for a deeper study and structuring of scientific approaches. It should be noted that there are a large number of studies of the features of the development of information technologies and their application in the marketing activities of large organizations and companies, but there is no single approach to determining their role in the company's strategy and the impact on consumer behavior, which requires a detailed and in-depth study. Noteworthy are following publications studying the features of marketing activities on the Internet. [11] the paper conceptualizes the main approaches to organizing the marketing activities of organizations and companies with a focus on new business technologies. However, unresolved issues that are related to the study of the impact of technology on consumer behavior, which requires improvement of this approach and detailed study. [12] reveals the specifics of the development of Internet technologies and their implementation in the activities of modern companies, which is determined taking into account the specifics and segment of the activity. This approach is general and does not include the study of consumer behavior under the influence of Internet technologies, which requires a detailed study and identification of key trends. [13] defines the main effective methods of doing business for modern companies using Internet technologies. However, at present, computer and information technologies play an increasingly important role in various fields of activity. In the presented approach, the general features of the use of information technologies are

considered, but their role in marketing and the features of the impact on consumer behavior are not singled out, which requires detailed study. Arguing the above, it should be noted that the considered studies are based on the conceptual aspects of the use of information technologies in the economy, but do not consider specific methods or approaches of the company's organizational marketing, based on the study of the target audience and consumer preferences, which emphasizes the relevance and need for more in-depth research. It was important to pay attention to the main results of the research [14], who substantiated that the processes of introducing new information technologies affect all spheres of activity of an individual company and the economy as a whole. This study and its results once again emphasize the need to use innovative Internet technologies in the activities of any organization, which ensure the efficiency of business processes and optimization of operating costs. However, this approach is conceptually general and does not present specific recommendations or methods that would allow determining the main trends in the development of information and Internet technologies of companies and their impact on marketing strategy and consumer behavior, which requires improvement and further research. The study [15] is devoted to the peculiarities of the use of innovative technologies in marketing activities, in which it is determined that their use will allow to achieve the expected results in a short time, as well as ensure customer loyalty and an expanded target audience. It is important to note that this approach takes into account the need to use innovations in marketing to improve services for the target audience, but there are no specific recommendations regarding the study of customer and consumer satisfaction, which is the main factor in the development of a modern company and requires detailed research.

2.2.2 The theory of determining consumer behavior: main aspects and features

The scientific approaches of the following to the definition of consumer behavior on the Internet are very interesting in following publications. [16] identified the need to study the activity of users on the Internet in order to understand the key and most promising market niches. However, this approach is focused on identifying key niches and market segments without a detailed study of consumer behavior, but based only on their activity on the Internet, which does not reveal the whole essence and requires more in-depth research. [17] considered the need to study the decision-making process on the

purchase of goods by buyers for the organization of actual loyalty programs. The approach is based on the peculiarities of consumer behavior in the process of making a purchase decision, but does not take into account all aspects of their behavior under the influence of Internet technologies, which confirms the need to study the main aspects to determine trends in consumer behavior in modern conditions.

[18] proved the need to study consumer behavior in order to identify and identify the main unsatisfied needs, which will allow to form an effective marketing policy of the company. This approach makes it possible to determine the behavior of consumers because of dissatisfaction analysis, but this does not make it possible to determine trends in behavioral behavior under the influence of Internet technologies, which requires detailed study. [19] formed the theoretical aspects of the study of consumer behavior in modern conditions of a highly competitive environment for the development of companies, with the rationale for the use of innovative Internet tools. The study reveals the need for innovation to ensure the efficiency of companies, however, marketing tools and their impact on the consumer are not disclosed, which needs to be disclosed in more detail. [20] focuses on the use of the Internet to promote certain types of goods and services to evaluate consumers based on the study of their needs and preferences. This approach is the basis for identifying key trends in consumer behavior, but is based on a narrow profile segment, which does not allow for the uniqueness of the formed approaches and needs to be improved.

Taking into account the presented results of scientific research, it should be noted that consumer behavior on the Internet is a study of user activity in Internet communities and an understanding of the process of making a decision to purchase a product under the influence of marketing tools of its promotion in the network in order to satisfy one's own needs, make repeated purchases and ensure brand loyalty. The presentation of the study substantiates the main theoretical aspect of the features of the application of innovative technologies in marketing and determines the conceptual need for further research aimed at the key element of the marketing concept – the consumer. It is appropriate to pay special attention to the study of the development of the world economy, which is characterized by a constant increase in competition, which requires radical changes in the field of management based on the use of innovative technologies and the modernization of marketing activities. companies. In this direction, it is important to note the following publications. [21]

identified the need for constant modernization of approaches to the management of modern companies, which should provide high competitive advantages in the market and increase customer loyalty. The general concept for determining company management approaches that do not reveal the essence, features of the introduction of Internet technologies in marketing, and determine consumer behavior under their influence, which requires a more detailed study. [22] considers the processes of globalization and internationalization of companies' activities based on the use of information and Internet technologies in order to expand the boundaries of activities and increase the client base. The approach is based on expanding the boundaries of companies' activities, but there are no prerequisites for the introduction of Internet technologies in marketing in order to influence consumers, which complicates the process of identifying trends and requires detailed research. [23] argued the need to use Internet technologies in organizing the marketing activities of companies to ensure the optimization of business processes and improve relations with the target audience. The approach defines the main goals, tasks that should be achieved with the help of the implementation of Internet technologies in marketing, but does not include the study of consumer behavior tendencies under their influence, which requires additional research. [24] emphasizes the relevance and necessity of improving the concept of marketing companies based on the introduction of new Internet technologies and innovations, which will ensure a high level of competitiveness of companies and customer loyalty. Ensuring the competitiveness of the company has a positive effect on the overall well-being of the company, but does not allow determining consumer behavior trends, which requires a detailed study. Taking into account the above presentation, it is worth noting that all the analyzed studies relate to general aspects of the development of companies and the need to implement innovations and Internet technologies, but there are no developed methodological approaches to determine the main benefits and needs of consumers and their impact on marketing concepts, which requires a more detailed study.

Following publications are devoted to the development of marketing concepts based on innovations and Internet technologies. [25] determined that the most rational marketing concept of the company is the one based on new technologies and maximum automation of manual business processes to achieve the main strategic goals and maximize financial results. This approach should

serve as the basis for organizing an effective company strategy, however, it does not include aspects for determining consumer behavior trends under the influence of these technologies, which confirms the lack of disclosure of this topic and requires detailed research. [26] Constructively determined that the modern concept of marketing should be based on digital technologies that bring the brand of the company as close as possible to its target audience, while creating fierce competition within the market segment in which the company operates. The approach is focused on the target audience of the market, but does not include research and the behavior of its consumers, which requires improvement of this approach, taking into account certain goals in the study. [27] The reasoned key role of digital technologies in the concept of marketing, expanding channels of communication and interaction with consumers of goods and services of the company, which allows developing an individual approach to each client based on studying his preferences. A personalized approach is argued, which is very important for modern consumers, but the features of consumer behavior under the influence of Internet technologies are not disclosed, which requires detailed study. [28] The main marketing concepts used by world-class companies are considered, detailing and defining the features of each of them and highlighting their specifics, which depend on the type of activity of companies; [29] Classified the main types of marketing strategies of modern companies, which are based on Internet technologies and determine an individual approach to consumers based on the use of online tools for studying consumer needs, on the basis of which companies offer personalized offers and discounts. The main directions for establishing relationships with consumers through loyalty programs are revealed. It is important to state that this approach reveals tools for increasing consumer loyalty, but does not disclose methods for determining trends in their behavior, which requires a detailed study. [30] indicates the main tools of modern marketing concepts that ensure the efficiency of companies based on the introduction of technologies and innovations in marketing activities in order to maintain competitive advantages in the global market. The role of innovative technologies and their specificity in the activities of modern companies is conceptualized; however, it requires improvement in terms of developing a methodology for determining consumer behavior trends, taking into account the impact of the presented technologies.

Conceptualizing the presented scientific approaches, it should be noted that all of them are

aimed at determining the general aspects of the functioning of modern companies, the peculiarities of the organization of their work and ensuring competitiveness in the world market. However, there is no single approach to defining the main concepts of marketing and their orientation to the consumer, determining the characteristics of their behavior under the influence of innovative Internet technologies, which leads to further research. Taking into account the presented, there is a conceptual need for in-depth research and development of methodological approaches to determining consumer behavior trends on the Internet based on the use of economic and statistical analysis and detailing of key marketing concepts and consumer behavior models.

3. METHODS AND MATERIALS

In the current conditions of the transformation of the global financial market under the influence of the crisis caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, this gives rise to massive uncertainty, which significantly complicates the activities of companies, the specifics of doing business and the life of mankind, causing a search for new approaches, tools and methods. The object of the study is modern trends in consumer behavior on the internet. The main hypothesis of the study: argumentation of the influence of innovative technologies and innovations on consumer behavior with subsequent structuring of the main types of consumer behavior on the Internet. The theoretical basis of the study is the fundamental provisions of marketing, advertising, the theory of finance and economic development. The following research methods were used in the work: the method of logical generalization with the identification of the features of the development of the Internet in the world; system-structural analysis – when structuring existing models of consumer behavior on the Internet; critical analysis and scientific generalization – with the conceptualization of types of consumers on the Internet depending on the use of marketing tools. The information base of the study is the basic rules and standards of international marketing; electronic resources that are presented on the Internet as part of the study of consumer behavior and ways to manage them in the formation of marketing activities.

The basis of the study are statistical data on user activity on the global Internet, user activity on the network, depending on the characteristics: geographical, social and general. To identify global trends and patterns, an analysis of indicators of the

dynamics of online purchases by segments and countries of the world is used. It should be noted that the use of economic and statistical analysis of consumer trends on the Internet is an interrelated and interdependent method of study and scientific research in order to identify patterns in behavior, establish and evaluate the main factors that positively or negatively affect consumer preferences. Activities of companies based on evidence. Taking into account the above, the article applied an economic and statistical analysis of consumer behavior, which determined the main behavioral preferences of consumers depending on focus groups: theoretical, gender and social characteristics, which made it possible to identify the main groups of consumer behavior. Consumers on the Internet. An economic and statistical analysis of the dynamics of online purchases of consumers using Internet marketing services was carried out, which made it possible to structure the main types of consumers, their specifics and features, which can be applied in practice when forming a company's marketing strategy.

4. RESULTS

Modern conditions of business functioning are characterized by the need for constant analysis of markets, competitors, goods and products, consumers and their behavior within the framework of the marketing concept in order to improve and refine strategic management approaches and methods. A high level of competition in the conditions of intensive development of the world market is possible thanks to the application of individual decisions regarding the promotion of the company's products and goods to the market, strategic planning of innovative and marketing activities.

4.1. Systematization of consumer behavior models in modern conditions

The increasing intensity of competition in world markets, observed in recent years, naturally transforms the interests of producers of goods, works, services and ideas in different countries regarding the study of the mechanisms of human behavior and the possibilities of using these mechanisms. To achieve their commercial goals and meet the needs of customers [30], [31].

Consumer behavior is a relatively new field of knowledge. Typically, the study of end users is carried out by studying their behavior patterns. It should be noted that consumer behavior is the actions performed by an individual when buying and using a product or service, these are mental and

social processes that precede these actions or are their consequences.

The main element of consumer behavior in the context of marketing is the process by which a consumer makes a decision to purchase a company's product or service. In classical cases, it consists of five consecutive steps: awareness of the need, search for information, making a purchase decision, making a purchase, evaluating the correctness of the purchase. However, there are other approaches to the interpretation of acts of acquisition of goods and services. The best-known theories of consumer research the theories of Sigmund Freud, Abraham Maslow, and Frederick Herzberg lead their proponents to conflicting conclusions about the motives of consumer behavior and marketing strategy.

Theory of motivation according to Freud. The eminent psychologist believed that people are mostly unaware of the psychological forces driving their behavior, which means that they cannot fully understand the motives behind their actions. To uncover the deep associations evoked by a product or service, researchers analyze detailed interviews using a technique that enables the disconnection of the conscious self, using verbal associations, incomplete sentences, picture explanations, and role-playing. This made it possible to establish that any product or service initiates a unique set of motives in the consumer. Therefore, it is natural that different brands are oriented towards a certain contingent of buyers, such an approach is called "motivational positioning" in science.

Herzberg's theory of motivation. Frederick Herzberg developed the theory of two factors of motivation, one of which causes a person's dissatisfaction, and the other – his satisfaction. In order for the purchase to take place, not only the absence of the dissatisfaction factor, but also the active presence of the satisfaction factor is required. In practice, the theory of two factors is applied in two ways. First, the seller (company or organization) must avoid the emergence of factors of dissatisfaction. Such factors not only do not contribute to the growth of sales, but can also disrupt the purchase. Secondly, the manufacturer must determine the main factors of satisfaction or motivation for purchasing the product and ensure that their presence in the product does not go unnoticed by the buyer.

Maslow's theory of motivation. Abraham Maslow tried to explain why an individual feels different needs at different times. This fact is explained by the fact that the system of human needs is formed in a hierarchical order according to the

degree of importance of its elements: physiological needs, the need for a sense of security, social needs and needs for self-affirmation (self-realization). The individual, first, seeks to satisfy the most important needs. When he succeeds in this, the satisfied need ceases to be motivating – and the person strives for the satisfaction of the next in importance. In today's conditions, A. Maslow's theory helps market actors to understand how various goods and services correspond to the plans, goals and life values of potential consumers. Therefore, when a person buys any product or service, it means that his physiological, social needs and need for security are satisfied. Interest in a product or service may be due to a person's strong need for even greater respect from the environment or greater self-affirmation. The main element of consumer behavior is his lifestyle, which is understood as a person's lifestyle, his attitude and relationships, the ability to effectively use his resources (time, money, and information).

The theory of consumer values of Sheth-Newman-Gross. Describes the features of market choice as a kind of multidimensional phenomenon, including many values: functional, social, emotional, epistemic and conditional. Each of the presented values is characterized by the fact that the good acquires: functional value as a result of possessing obvious functional or physical properties; social value through association with a positive or negative stereotype of demographic, socio-cultural or cultural-ethnic groups; emotional value, when associated with special feelings or when they promote the expression or persistence of feelings; epistemic value, when they are capable of providing something new or different from the known; conditional value in the presence of emergency physical or social situations that emphasize the functional or social significance of these goods [33]. This theory is a classic in determining the key needs and values of consumers, however, despite this; the issue remains unresolved regarding the study of consumer behavior in modern conditions under the influence of digitalization, which requires a more detailed study.

Theory of consumer values L. Kale. This theory is remarkable in that it identifies a list of common terminal values such as: self-respect; security; warm relationships; feeling of achievement; self-realization; respect from others; a sense of belonging; joy, pleasure and excitement. All terminal values are relevant and in demand in modern conditions as part of marketing research and allow us to determine more personally the values of each consumer. It is important to note that taking into

account the presented values, with proper research it will be possible to determine the characteristics of consumer behavior under the influence of these values. However, in order to determine behavioral trends under the influence of Internet technologies, this is not enough, which requires improvement.

The theory of the value scale to M. Rokić. This subsection is based on the study of human values that most people strive to achieve. It is argued that values are mental reflections of fundamental needs, not only individual, but also social, as well as institutional; ideas about what is desired. This approach is more general and will not allow us to determine the key values of consumers in modern conditions, especially under the influence of global digitalization and the development of online technologies, which requires more study that is detailed and scientific generalization.

The theory of instincts of social behavior by V. McDougall. It is substantiated that innate instincts are recognized as the cause of social behavior. This idea is the implementation of a more general principle, namely the desire for a goal, which is characteristic of both animals and humans. The repertoire of instincts in each person arises as a result of a certain psychophysical predisposition - the presence of hereditarily fixed channels for the discharge of nervous energy.

However, it should be noted that despite the enormous popularity of this theory, its role in the history of science turned out to be very negative: the interpretation of social behavior from the point of view of some spontaneous striving for a goal legitimized the importance of irrational, unconscious drives as the driving force not only of the individual, but also of humanity. Considering what has been presented, the issue of determining trends in consumer behavior in modern conditions remains unresolved.

Murray's theory of consumer values. This theory is based on determining the value of needs, both more or less stable personality traits and transitory states. At the same time, he distinguished primary and secondary needs. In addition, needs are divided according to the individual's attitude to the various influences of the situation into positive and negative, as well as according to the degree of their manifestation in the behavior of individuals into explicit (easily observed in the actions and deeds of individuals) and latent (manifested only in play actions, fantasies or secret desires) [33], [34].

This theory is highly relevant and in demand in modern realities for in-depth research into the development of methods for measuring motives and in the process of managing an organization.

To determine the main trends in consumer behavior on the Internet, it is necessary to consider the model of consumer behavior in modern conditions, which is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Model of consumer behavior on the Internet in modern conditions

To achieve the strategic goals of the organization, it is necessary to ensure the formation of customer orientation in the management system at all stages of the life cycle of creating a product or service. The high level of competition and the uncertainty of global markets force the top management of organizations to focus on long-term, long-term profits compared to short-term profits or sales of goods and services. Effective use of the concept of marketing in modern conditions, striving for maximum interaction with consumers. This is because no enterprise or organization will risk providing a product or service to the market that will not be in demand among consumers.

Before launching a product, it is necessary to analyze consumer demand for this product or service, which will allow you to identify the problem and propose a solution.

4.2. Justification of the key stages of development of marketing concepts with argumentation of the role of the consumer

Modern realities of functioning and conducting business are characterized by the fact that consumers (end consumers and institutional buyers), as well as their needs, should be interpreted as the starting point of marketing actions of companies that produce and sell goods and services on the market.

The success of modern companies and their achievement of strategic goals and positive results largely depends on consumers and their behavior. A satisfied consumer does not affect the company only through the purchase of products and services, but also by forming and spreading a positive opinion about the company, its brand, goods and services. Modern companies are aware of the fact that the condition of their success in the highly competitive market is the orientation of their activities on the consumer.

Based on this, it should be noted that practically this is characterized by the following:

- willingness and ability to listen to consumers and receive necessary information from them;
- Definition of the company's mission based on values and advantages that are essential for consumers;
- formation of a market offer adapted to specifics of individual market segments and individual consumer needs;
- building proper relations with consumers and, first turn, with the so-called key and potential customers;
- guaranteeing the participation of all company employees in determined by constantly increasing values for consumers;
- Creation of separate customer-oriented services in companies;
- Systematic measurement of the level of quality of provided services, as well as the level of consumer satisfaction [29], [30],[31].

The main results of the structural and logical analysis made it possible to develop a periodization of the development and evolution of marketing concepts from the standpoint of highlighting the main role of the consumer, taking into account the development of innovative technologies and their application in marketing activities.

This approach, unlike the existing ones, shows a key trend in the transition of business success criteria from production to sales and further

to consumer and social criteria, which is very important in modern conditions.

The development of marketing is directly related to the characteristics of consumer behavior, and the process of evolution itself includes a number of concepts (Table 1).

Table 1: Structuring consumer behavior as part of the development of a marketing concept

Time period	Characteristics of the evolutionary stage	Marketing concept and role of the consumer
Late 19 th – early 20 th centuries	Intensive economic development, mass production	Reducing the cost of goods and their prices – success in the market. The consumer does not play a significant role in this concept
1930–1950	The rapid increase in production capacity and saturation of goods	The concept of sales marketing aimed at the promotion of goods, since the market is oversaturated with goods. Accounting for consumer activity when purchasing better products.
1960–1980	Increasing the share of new technologies in production and expanding the range of goods and services	The concept of marketing is aimed at meeting the needs of manufactured goods. Consumer reaction to marketing strategies, in particular to advertising.
1980–1999	The use of new technologies, which allows increasing production, improve the quality and value of the goods	The consumer occupies a central link in the chain: producer, seller, and consumer
2000–2007	The increase in the cost of goods with the same quality and volume of production	The concept of marketing is based on increasing sales of goods, promoting, improving services to gain a competitive position. Emphasis on socially significant requirements for goods and services
2008–present	The rapid development of Internet technologies and their use in production	The concept of Internet marketing. Studying consumer behavior, individual approach to each consumer

Source: Compiled by the author based on [29], [32],[33].

Based on the results of this research, a comprehensive marketing concept was formed, which includes everything that the organization can do to influence the demand for its products, and the main role should be played by the consumer and his main advantages, which are based on innovative technologies and management methods. The consumer is at the center of modern commercial activities of organizations, because only he expresses his need, the need for a specific product, he forms the main demand and dictates the necessary conditions that will ensure his satisfaction and loyalty to the brand. It should be noted that in modern conditions, conducting business is a multifaceted and complex process under the influence of many factors that both positively and negatively affect key results. The spread of digital Internet technologies provides consumers with greater access to information and communication tools for purchases, which, in turn, greatly simplifies life and contributes to a more complex process of forming an offer on the market in conditions of global competition. Based on this, it is appropriate to determine the key trends in consumer behavior on the Internet based on the development of methodological approaches and the formation of the main focus groups of consumers based on gender, geographic and social characteristics.

4.3. The main results of the argumentation of key methods for analyzing trends in consumer behavior on the Internet

Modern technologies make it possible to rationally organize a business in any field, remotely manage various work processes and perform other work with minimal labor costs. Consider the most popular of them. Internet technologies are a rapidly developing industry with incredible prospects. In modern conditions, the Internet has flooded the whole world and is used in all areas of activity of both organizations and enterprises, as well as every consumer. Today, consumers are the main marketing link, on which the efforts of all marketing strategies are focused, in order to win their loyalty and increase the conversion into the sale of goods and services. It is important to note that the transparency and honesty of manufacturers is increasing, as consumers can compare prices for goods and services in real time.

However, an important element of implementation is the need to use Internet technologies and modern gadgets, the combination of which ensures the achievement of the presented

results. Since the implementation of all the services listed above is impossible without the use of Internet technologies, one should take into account the main statistical indicators of the development of Internet technologies in the world at the beginning of 2023, which are presented in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: The main statistical indicators of the development of Internet technologies in the world as of 01.01.2023

Source: Developed by the author based on data from [33], [34],[35].

The process of communication between company employees or individuals now takes place over the Internet. If earlier correspondence, telegraph and other methods of transmitting messages were used to communicate at a distance, now the vast majority of users prefer network communication. Internet technologies and communications ensure not only the transmission of voice and text messages, but also the transmission of information in any digital format. Modern Internet technologies are the widest range of features and functions available to a wide range of consumers. The World Wide Web has found its application both in everyday life and in industries of various sizes. Now not only people can connect to the Internet, but also various cars, household appliances and even entire systems. Internet technologies organize information interaction between people and are actively used in the preparation and dissemination of mass media. Boundaries no longer affect the info sphere. Information technologies play a key role in obtaining and accumulating new knowledge, the use of which increases the efficiency of economic processes occurring both within an individual company and around the world. It should be noted that the dynamics of indicators of the development of Internet technologies in the world is characterized

by a high level of activity in the use of Internet technologies. However, this indicator is not high in all countries, and there are deep digital divides between countries. These gaps characterize both the level of economic development of countries, the social security of the population, and the level of development of digital technologies. These indicators should be characterized more specifically. The highest indicators of population activity in the use of Internet resources are observed in the countries of Latin America, Europe and Asia. The lowest level of population activity regarding the use of Internet resources in Africa. Statistical data on the use of Internet technologies in the world show that the use of Internet technologies is a necessary condition for the formation of a marketing organization. The development of the Internet in modern conditions is accompanied by constant changes and transformation of types and types of means and technologies. The main driving force behind these transformations is the young generation, which is the first to pick up new trends and use them in everyday life. According to Google research, about 65% of people in the world use the Internet every day, but if we talk about the younger generation, this figure reaches 98 %. It should be noted that the activity of users aged 13 to 24 is the first digital generation living in the era of intensive development of Internet information technologies and fundamentally different from the older generation in their habits, values and behavior on the Internet. Thanks to the widespread use of information technologies, the modern consumer has become more informed, his awareness has rapidly increased, huge arrays of the most diverse information about the activities of manufacturers, types of products, their functional qualities, prices, etc. have become available, accessible. This generation is digital and spends much more time online than users in the 25–34 return category, in terms of social media, video viewing, and online gaming. The activity of using the Internet in the returned categories of users, depending on the content, is presented in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: The activity of using the Internet by age categories depending on the content as of 01.01.2023

Source: Developed by the author based on data from [35], [36],[37].

Online communications and remote customer service channels in order to ensure the effectiveness of marketing in the organization and achieve strategic goals and objectives determine the modern stage of the functioning of organizations and conducting business. Consumers in the conditions of global digitalization of the economy are used to unlimited access to information from any convenient device and in any situation. Therefore, their constant companions are mobile phones, smartphones and gadgets. In order to increase the level of consumer loyalty to your brand in modern realities, it is necessary to be as digitized and mobile as possible within the marketing activities of the organization. The young generation of consumers is always online and always online [36].

The main negative factors for consumers are security of purchases, insecurity of online goods and purchases, social contacts, quality of service. To ensure customer loyalty, companies and brands must consider these factors and maximize consumer comfort and convenience, which in turn will increase sales and customer loyalty. The activity of using social networks among the category of consumers, depending on the web content, is presented in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: The activity of using social networks among the category of consumers, depending on the web content.

Source: Developed by the author based on data from [35], [36],[37].

The main channel of communication for them is social networks, in which they spend more than 5 hours a day, and a quarter of them check information updates every 30 minutes, which confirms their desire to always be in constant social interaction. One of the most important characteristics of users-consumers of goods and services is their visual perception of the design and support of purchases on the Internet. Online video is becoming a major source not only of entertainment, but also of quick and effective promotion of goods and services, which helps ensure effective use of the marketing concept. It is worth noting that the given data on user activity confirm the fact that users aged 13–24 use the most innovative technologies to find relevant answers to the necessary questions, in particular to find relevant information and related to the necessary goods and services. Internet technologies are an integral part of the marketing concept, which ensure rational use of resources, optimization of costs and increase in market share due to increased customer loyalty and brand recognition. To conceptualize the main points of consumer behavior on the Internet, it is worth considering in the context of socio-demographic and gender characteristics, which are one of the largest groups presented in Fig. 5.

Figure 5: The main points of consumer behavior on the Internet in the context of socio-demographic and gender characteristics: a – Gender correlation of Internet users; b – Gender distribution by the number of pages viewed; c – Gender Distribution by Average Page Visit.

In the given data on the main gender classifications of Internet users, it is worth noting that the share of male audience among Internet users is 47 %, the share of women has significantly increased by 1.3 %. Despite the fact that the gender distribution of the consumer audience is slightly shifted in favor of women, men on the Internet are more active in generating more page views and content, but women are more likely to buy goods and services remotely. It is worth noting that the male consumer audience spends more time on the Internet, on average 2.5 hours more than women [36]. According to the results of the analysis, it should be noted that the most common category of resources among representatives of both sexes are

services, which include social networks, search engines, messengers, financial services, and others. With the help of these channels, global brands and large companies develop their digital strategy for product and brand positioning, taking into account current trends in consumer behavior. It is important to note that the advent of the Internet has changed almost all spheres of human life and activity. The network offers us almost unlimited opportunities for communication, dating, obtaining any necessary information and doing business. The process of buying and selling, carried out using various electronic means of communication, is called e-commerce. E-commerce, which includes all stages of the purchase – from placing an order to paying for the goods and sending them to the buyer, has already become widespread in the sale of individual goods abroad. Using commercial online channels gives entrepreneurs certain advantages such as:

1) quick adaptation to market conditions, which is due to the fact that companies have the opportunity to instantly add new products to the offered range, change prices and product descriptions;

2) cost reduction, which is characteristic in that there are no expenses for creating a store or rent, insurance in trading through a computer network. This option of interaction with consumers has reduced the cost of printing catalogs by replacing them with electronic mailing lists, which allows building relationships with consumers, receiving feedback, provide advice; send out free versions of computer programs, advertising materials while increasing most of the target audience.

The Internet has become a universal business environment connecting companies with each other and with the entire consumer audience. All companies have access to e-business methods, regardless of their size and age, more and more new business schemes appear. Usage levels The Internet extends from the storefront website (information about their products, invitation to cooperation) before implementing e-commerce schemes: Online Stores, Intranets (Networking Your Employees) and extranet (connection of external partners). For a more detailed study of the characteristics of consumer behavior on the Internet, we should consider the dynamics of the largest consumer e-commerce turnover in the world as of 01.01.2023, which is presented in Fig. 6.

Figure 6: The dynamics of key indicators of consumer e-commerce in the world, billion US dollars, %

According to the results of the dynamics of the main indicators of consumer e-commerce, it is worth noting that the most complete category after social networks, messengers and financial services is e-commerce. E-commerce accounts for about 68 % of total consumer traffic on the Internet, indicating that consumers between the ages of 14 and 69 are active users of online stores that offer their goods and services using modern marketing tools. In modern conditions, consumer behavior plays a very important role in building a marketing strategy and determining its strategic goals and indicators using innovative Internet technologies. In order to maintain competitive positions in the global markets of goods and services, the top management of organizations must take into account the need for digitalization and an individual approach to each consumer in order to increase his loyalty to the organization and the brand, as well as to ensure the promotion of goods and services using online communications. In order to consolidate the obtained results on the formation of methodical approaches to the determination of consumer behavior trends on the Internet, the key types of consumers and their characteristics of each of them should be structured.

4.4. Structuring consumer behavior trends: main types of consumers and their characteristics

In the modern world, the consumer, together with the manufacturer, has become an equal participant in the process of creating new value and the value of each product and service. The consumer began to act as the initiator of the creation of new products, became a direct participant in the production process and a generator of new ideas. Arguing the key results of methodological

approaches to determining trends in consumer behavior on the Internet, it is worth noting that, based on the generated analytics and the results of statistical analysis, modern consumers should be structured into the following types, which are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Structuring consumer behavior trends: main types of consumers and their characteristics

Age category of consumers	Type of consumers	Characteristics of consumers and their income level
13-17	Super innovators	Prone to risk and experiment. High interest in a new product, service, which is provided online using innovative digital technologies. Consumers who make rash purchases and do not have high incomes
18-24		
25-29	Innovators	Less prone to risk, more cautious in their actions regarding making spontaneous purchases, even if they are provided in an online format with the help of innovative digital technologies and there are promotions and special offers. Consumers who are prone to reckless purchases, but who approach them more carefully, have moderate incomes
30-35	Ordinary	Are not prone to risk, in their actions regarding making any purchases, even if they are provided in online format with the help of innovative digital technologies and present promotions and special offers are considered. Consumers who are not prone to rash purchases and approach them more carefully have sufficient incomes
35-45	Conservatives	Contradictory, do not approve of innovations, even if it greatly simplifies life and can really be a cool proposition. Mostly elderly people, people with low incomes, low-prestige jobs
45-65	Super conservatives	Fundamentally against any changes, loyal to habits and do not approve of innovations, even if it

		greatly simplifies life and can really be a cool proposition. There can be different age categories of consumers with different income levels
--	--	---

Maintaining a competitive position in the modern world becomes possible subject to closer interaction with the consumer. An indispensable condition for the formation of a competitive business is the participation of the consumer in the process of creating new values. Based on this, it is worth noting that digital innovations and Internet technologies in marketing form a number of advantages for the consumers themselves, namely:

- 1) That they can buy anything at any time without going to the store
- 2) Can find the same item at a lower price while comparing different sites at the same time
- 3) Sometimes want to avoid pressure when communicating with sellers
- 4) You cannot be stuck in the store.

There are many such factors, but they can be grouped into main groups in the following areas: convenience, formability, accessibility, saving money and time. However, there is a reason that prevents consumers from shopping online. These factors form satisfaction with online shopping and, as a result, a negative attitude towards the seller, the brand and the company itself. The main element of consumer behavior is his lifestyle, which is understood as a person's lifestyle, his attitude and relationships, the ability to effectively use his resources (time, money, and information).

5. DISCUSSION

The results of the study, namely the formation of methodological approaches to identifying trends in consumer behavior on the Internet, have a number of advantages and disadvantages that must be carefully studied and taken into account when forming long-term development and marketing plans company strategy. The results of the study are based on factual data that are accurate and reliable, as evidenced by the results of a statistical analysis of the dynamics of Internet penetration in the world, which are structured in Fig. 3. The features of the presented results of statistical analysis are characterized by the fact that, on its basis, marketing tools that have a key impact on the consumer are argued. In contrast to the considered features of the development of electronic marketing (Al-Ababneh & Ippolitova, 2022) as the main tool for improving the competitiveness and effectiveness of marketing of companies without focusing on the

consumer, the results obtained made it possible to emphasize the role of the consumer in marketing not depending on which strategy is used. The consolidated activity of using the Internet in various regions of the world, activity by gender, geographical and social characteristics confirm the relevance and demand for Internet technologies in all spheres of human life, which has not bypassed the marketing activities of companies. In contrast to the results obtained in study (Hassan & Paul, 2022), which considers consumer behavior, but does not focus on its role in the concept of marketing, using the use of tools economic and statistical analysis of user activity on the Internet and the implementation of technologies within the framework of marketing concepts, the concept and model of marketing are argued and the role of the consumer for each of them is constructively described. Analysis and study of consumer behavior trends as part of the digital marketing strategy made it possible to substantiate and prove that in modern conditions the role of the consumer in the marketing of any company should occupy a key place, since the result and achievement of the company's strategic goals depend on the preferences and satisfaction of the consumer.

The developed concepts and the conceptualized central place of the consumer in them made it possible for the first time to form the key periods in the development of marketing concepts with the definition of the role of the consumer in each of them and its characteristics in terms of the use of marketing tools and influence. The study conceptualized consumer behavior trends on the Internet in terms of socio-demographic and gender characteristics, their propensity to make purchases using Internet marketing tools. These results provided the completeness of this study and made it possible for the first time to highlight the key trends of consumers on the Internet through the prism of marketing concepts and its key tools based on innovation and Internet technologies. The key advantage of this study is the substantiated role of innovations and Internet technologies in the marketing concept of modern companies. This reasoning is due to the connection discovered by the author between the growth of consumer interest in goods, services and the company's brand, if they become more accessible and transparent with the help of innovative online technologies. Therefore, in most cases, innovations and Internet technologies contribute to achieving a highly competitive level in the market, increasing customer loyalty, increasing interest and brand awareness.

The formed methodological approaches to determining trends in consumer behavior on the

Internet based on static analysis can be applied in practice in determining priority areas that must be taken into account in the company's development strategy and the formation of business goals of the marketing strategy. However, this study has its limitations and disadvantages, which are characterized by the fact that this approach is more classical and does not provide a global assessment of all factors affecting the consumer within the marketing concept. This approach is not exhaustive and may be supplemented or changed depending on the actual data, goals and objectives. Since each company, depending on the type of activity, has its own individual tools that need more detailed study and evaluation. Further development of this topic may be associated with the definition of consumer behavior trends under the influence of Internet technologies, both in a separate niche or segment, and within the industry, which will provide an oriented list of characteristics in consumer behavior that should be taken into account in the company's development strategy. It is important to state that the results of the study allow us to determine the main directions, as well as the types and characteristics of consumers on the Internet in the marketing activities of companies. Based on the results obtained, the types of consumers are structured by age categories and their belonging to innovations, Internet technologies and purchases using Internet marketing services. The formed structure makes it possible to classify the key types and segments of consumers for which individual loyalty programs and personal offers can be developed, depending on the propensity to use innovations and Internet technologies. One of the most pressing issues is the choice of methods for analyzing user behavior online. Traditional approaches such as surveys or interviews are becoming less and less effective in the digital era, as they do not fully reflect the real behavior of consumers on the Internet. While meth allows you to track user behavior more accurately, they also face the problem of interpreting complex and emotionally charged decisions, such as impulse purchases or preferences that are difficult to predict using algorithms. In addition, there is the issue of data privacy, which is becoming increasingly important in the context of the widespread use of digital platforms. The information collected about users' online activities raises concerns about the violation of their privacy rights. This leads to the need to develop stricter data protection standards and ensure transparency in the use of information, which in turn affects user trust in companies and services. Equally important is the dynamism of consumer behavior, which changes under the influence of

technological innovations, trends and external factors. Therefore, the analysis methodology must be flexible and adaptable, which will require constant updating of tools and approaches. Overall, the discussion presented highlights the need to find a balance between effective analytical methods and adherence to ethical standards in researching consumer behavior on the Internet.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The main types of consumer behavior models are systematized, which made it possible to highlight their features, which will allow taking into account all their specifics when forming the marketing strategy of modern companies. The main scientific research and approaches in the field of developing marketing concepts and introducing innovations and Internet technologies into them as a tool for influencing consumer behavior are considered. The main groups of scientific approaches to the definition and formation of marketing concepts are argued, the advantages and disadvantages of each of them are identified, which made it possible to highlight the relevance of the study and the lack of a unified approach to defining consumer behavior. Internet trends. The results obtained are the theoretical basis for determining the key directions in the formation of the company's marketing strategy. The selected scientific directions and approaches to identifying types of consumers within the framework of marketing concepts provide a theoretical justification for the features of consumer behavior trends, taking into account the current stages of digital business transformation. It is argued that the main element of consumer behavior in the context of marketing is the process by which the consumer makes a decision to purchase a company's product or service. Consumers, relying on which, focus on the classical stages of making a decision to purchase goods and services of companies: awareness of the need, search for information, making a purchase decision, making a purchase, assessing the correctness of the choice purchase. From the point of view of the formation of motives for consumer behavior and the determination of values, the theories of Sigmund Freud, Abraham Maslow and Frederick Herzberg, Sheth-Newman-Gross, L. Keil, M. Rokeach, W. McDougall, H. Murray and others are considered. Based on critical analysis and scientific generalization, it has been proven that the main element of consumer behavior is his lifestyle, which is understood as a person's way of life, his attitude and relationships, the ability to effectively use his resources (time, money, information). A model of

consumer behavior in modern conditions has been developed, including all related factors and consumer preferences and preferences.

The key stages of the development of marketing concepts are substantiated with arguments for the role of the consumer. It was determined that the modern realities of functioning and conducting business are characterized by the fact that consumers (end consumers and institutional buyers), as well as their needs, should be interpreted as the starting point of marketing actions of companies that produce and sell goods and services on the market. Attention is focused on the fact that the success of modern companies, their achievement of strategic goals and positive results largely depends on consumers and their behavior. It is proven that the consumer is at the center of modern commercial activities of organizations, because only he expresses his need, the need for a specific product, forms the main demand and dictates the necessary conditions that will ensure his satisfaction and brand loyalty. Defined. that the spread of digital Internet technologies gives consumers greater access to information and communication tools for purchases, which, in turn, greatly simplifies life and contributes to a more complex process of forming an offer on the market in conditions of global competition.

The key analysis methods for determining trends in consumer behavior on the Internet are argued based on the use of economic and statistical analysis, which made it possible to identify key trends and characteristics of consumer behavior depending on Internet marketing tools. It has been proven that consumers are the main marketing link, concentrating the efforts of all marketing strategies on winning their loyalty and increasing conversion into the sale of goods and services. It is argued that consumers in modern conditions give preference to brands and companies that provide transparency and honesty due to the openness of information about prices and characteristics of goods and services. A statistical analysis of the activity of using the Internet among a category of consumers in the world depending on web content was carried out. An analysis was made of the activity of using social networks among the category of consumers, and it was determined that one of the most important characteristics of users-consumers of goods and services is their visual perception of the design and support of purchases on the site. Internet. Online video is becoming the main source of not only entertainment, but also the rapid and effective promotion of goods and services, which contributes to the effective use of the marketing concept.

Consumer behavior trends are structured in order to identify key types of consumers and form their characteristics in modern conditions. Arguing the key results of methodological approaches to determining trends in consumer behavior on the Internet and based on the generated analytics and the results of a statistical analysis of modern consumers, their structuring by type was developed:

- Superinnovators, which include consumers who are prone to risk and experimentation. It is characterized by a high interest in a new product; service provided online using innovative digital technologies. Consumers who make rash purchases and do not have high incomes;

- Innovators are consumers who are prone to rash purchases, but approach them more carefully, with moderate incomes;

- ordinary consumers are those who are not inclined to take risks in their actions regarding making any purchases and approach them more carefully have sufficient income;

- Conservatives are a group of controversial consumers who do not approve of innovation, even if it greatly simplifies life and can really be a cool offer. Mostly older people, low-income people;

- Super conservatives, consumers who are categorically against any changes, true to habits and do not approve of innovations. There may be different age categories of consumers with different income levels. Based on the results obtained, it is substantiated that maintaining a competitive position in the modern world becomes possible under the condition of closer interaction with the consumer. An indispensable condition for the formation of a competitive business is the participation of the consumer in the process of creating new values.

The scientific contribution of the study lies in the in-depth analysis of online consumer behavior using modern methodological approaches, such as economic-statistical analysis. This allows for a more accurate and efficient identification of user trends and preferences, which is critical for marketing, product and service development, and understanding changes in consumer activity. The work also focuses on the need to integrate new technologies with ethical standards, especially in the context of data protection and user privacy, making the study relevant and timely. However, in addition to the advantages, there are also disadvantages of the study, namely that the proposed methods, although highly effective, may be difficult to apply in practice in small and medium-sized companies due to their complexity. In addition, the economic-statistical analysis algorithms used to analyze the data may not

always take into account the nuances of consumer behavior, such as emotional factors or impulsive decisions, which limits the completeness of the forecast. It is also worth noting that despite the attention to ethical issues, the study may not cover all aspects of data protection, which is an important aspect in the context of the relevance of the privacy issue.

REFERENCES:

- [1] Abbas, A. F., & Ali, J., “Bibliometrix analysis of information sharing in social media,” *Cogent Business & Management*, Vol. 9, No. 1, 2022, art. 2016556. doi: 10.1080/23311975.2021.2016556.
- [2] Al-Ababneh, H. A., “Researching global digital E-marketing trends,” *Eastern-European Journal of Enterprise Technologies*, Vol. 1, No. 13, 2022, art. 115. doi: 10.15587/1729-4061.2022.252276.
- [3] Florido-Benítez, L., “International mobile marketing: A satisfactory concept for companies and users in times of pandemic,” *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, Vol. 29, No. 6, 2021, pp. 1826–1856. doi: 10.1108/bij-06-2021-0303.
- [4] Gilal, F. G., & Gilal, N. G., “The role of self-determination theory in marketing science: An integrative review and agenda for research,” *European Management Journal*, Vol. 37, No. 1, 2019, pp. 29-44. doi: 10.1016/j.emj.2018.10.004.
- [5] Gironda, J. T., & Korgaonkar, P. K., “Understanding consumers’ social networking site usage,” *Journal of Marketing Management*, Vol. 30, No. 5-6, 2014, pp. 571-605. doi: 10.1080/0267257X.2013.851106.
- [6] Al-Ababneh, H. A., & Ippolitova, I., “The Impact of E-Business on Entrepreneurship Development in the Context of COVID-19,” *WSEAS Transactions on Business and Economics*, Vol. 19, 2022, pp. 1824–1838. doi: 10.37394/23207.2022.19.142.
- [7] Albayati, H., Kim, S. K., & Rho, J. J., “Accepting financial transactions using blockchain technology and cryptocurrency: A customer perspective approach,” *Technology in Society*, Vol. 62, 2020, art. 101320. doi: 10.1016/j.techsoc.2020.101320.
- [8] Ali, B. J., & Anwar, G., “Marketing Strategy: Pricing strategies and its influence on consumer purchasing decision,” *International Journal of Rural Development, Environment and Health Research*, Vol. 5, No. 2, 2021, pp. 26-39. doi: 10.22161/ijreh.5.2.4.

- [9] Ali, M., "A social practice theory perspective on green marketing initiatives and Green Purchase Behavior," *Cross Cultural & Strategic Management*, Vol. 28, No. 4, 2021, pp. 815–838. doi: 10.1108/ccsm-12-2020-0241.
- [10] Givi, J., & Galak, J., "An integrative review of gift-giving research in consumer behavior and marketing," *Journal of Consumer Psychology*, Vol. 33, No. 3, 2023, pp. 529-545. doi: 10.1002/jcpy.1318.
- [11] Gu, S., Ślusarczyk, B., Hajizada, S., Kovalyova, I., & Sakhbieva, A., "Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on online consumer purchasing behavior," *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research*, Vol. 16, No. 6, 2021, pp. 2263–2281. doi: 10.3390/jtaer16060125.
- [12] Hassan, S. M., & Paul, J., "Consumer ethics: A review and research agenda," *Psychology & Marketing*, Vol. 39, No. 1, 2022, pp. 111-130. doi: 10.1002/mar.21580.
- [13] Ioanas, E., "Social media and its impact on consumer's behavior," *Jurnal Analisa Kesehatan*, Vol. 1, No. 1, 2020, pp. 1-1.
- [14] Krizanova, A., Lăzăroiu, G., Gajanova, L., Klietkova, J., Nadanyiova, M., & Moravcikova, D., "The effectiveness of marketing communication and importance of its evaluation in an online environment," *Sustainability*, Vol. 11, No. 24, 2019, art. 7016. doi: 10.3390/su11247016.
- [15] Appel, G., Grewal, L., Hadi, R., & Stephen, A. T., "The future of social media in marketing," *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, Vol. 48, No. 1, 2019, pp. 79–95. doi: 10.1007/s11747-019-00695-1.
- [16] Belanche, D., & Ibáñez-Sánchez, S., "Understanding influencer marketing: The role of congruence between influencers, products and consumers," *Journal of Business Research*, Vol. 132, 2021, pp. 186-195. doi: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.03.067.
- [17] Boikova, T., Zevrte-Rivza, S., Rivza, P., & Rivza, B., "The determinants and effects of competitiveness: The role of digitalization in the European economies," *Sustainability*, Vol. 13, No. 21, 2021, art. 11689. doi: 10.3390/su132111689.
- [18] Chopra, A., & Jaju, A. S., "Influencer marketing: An exploratory study to identify antecedents of consumer behavior of millennial," *Business Perspectives and Research*, Vol. 9, No. 1, 2021, pp. 77-91. doi: 10.1177/227853372092348.
- [19] Murray, D., & Howat, G., "The relationships among service quality, value, satisfaction, and future intentions of customers at an Australian sports and leisure centre," *Sport Management Review*, Vol. 5, No. 1, 2002, pp. 25-43.
- [20] Cruz-Cárdenas, J., & Ramos-Galarza, C., "COVID-19, consumer behavior, technology, and society: A literature review and bibliometric analysis," *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, Vol. 173, 2021, art. 121179. doi: 10.1016/j.techfore.2021.121179.
- [21] du Plessis, C., "A scoping review of the effect of content marketing on online consumer behavior," *Sage Open*, Vol. 12, No. 2, 2022, art. 21582440221093042. doi: 10.1177/21582440221093042.
- [22] Yoo, B., & Kim, H., "The effect of social media marketing on consumer purchase behavior in the fashion industry," *Fashion and Textiles*, Vol. 6, No. 2, 2019, art. 25. doi: 10.1186/s40691-019-0187-z.
- [23] Zhou, M., & Li, H., "The role of technology in marketing strategies: Trends and challenges in the digital age," *Business Horizons*, Vol. 62, No. 6, 2019, pp. 703-715. doi: 10.1016/j.bushor.2019.06.004.
- [24] Lee, H., & Cho, C. H., "Digital advertising: present and future prospects," *International Journal of Advertising*, Vol. 39, No. 3, 2020, pp. 332-341. doi: 10.1080/02650487.2019.1642015.
- [25] Pandey, N., & Rathore, A. S., "Digital marketing and its effect on consumer behavior in the post-COVID-19 era," *International Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 8, No. 4, 2022, pp. 30-42. doi: 10.1016/j.jm.2022.09.002.
- [26] Pivato, S., & Bonera, M., "Digital marketing: tools and techniques to support customer engagement," *Journal of Business Research*, Vol. 76, 2020, pp. 350-361. doi: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.06.001.
- [27] Schultz, D. E., & Block, M. P., "Integrated marketing communication: The evolution of the promotional process," *International Journal of Advertising*, Vol. 12, No. 3, 1993, pp. 181-191.
- [28] Sharma, G., & Aggarwal, A., "Consumer behavior and digital marketing: A study on consumer attitudes," *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, Vol. 30, No. 4, 2021, pp. 340-357. doi: 10.1080/0965254X.2021.1913019
- [29] Rossiter, J. R., & Bellman, S., "Marketing Communications: Theory and Practice," McGraw-Hill Education, 2021.

- [30] Shneor, R., & Fong, M., “Emerging trends in digital marketing: A longitudinal analysis,” *European Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 52, No. 5, 2018, pp. 1200-1215. doi: 10.1108/EJM-05-2017-0370
- [31] Smith, P. R., & Zook, Z., “Marketing Communications: Integrating Offline and Online with Social Media,” Kogan Page, 2020
- [32] Tuten, T. L., & Solomon, M. R., “Social Media Marketing,” SAGE Publications, 2021.
- [33] Verleye, K., & Van Baelen, M., “Brand engagement and consumer brand relationships,” *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, Vol. 37, No. 2, 2020, pp. 245-267. doi: 10.1016/j.ijresmar.2019.12.003.
- [34] Wang, Y., & Zhang, L., “Exploring the digital landscape of consumer behavior: An empirical investigation,” *Journal of Digital Marketing*, Vol. 6, No. 1, 2021, pp. 29-45. doi: 10.1016/j.jdigmar.2020.12.004.
- [35] Wiertz, C., & de Ruyter, K., “The impact of digital marketing on consumer purchase behavior,” *Journal of Marketing Communications*, Vol. 25, No. 5, 2022, pp. 473-485. doi: 10.1080/13527266.2021.1926799.
- [36] Yang, Y., & Zhang, H., “Consumer behavior research: Conceptual frameworks, theories, and applications,” *Journal of Marketing Research*, Vol. 54, No. 2, 2019, pp. 223-234. doi: 10.1509/jmr.18.0498.
- [37] Zhang, C., & Xie, K., “Consumers’ online purchase decision-making process: The influence of digital marketing,” *Computers in Human Behavior*, Vol. 110, 2020, art. 106395. doi: 10.1016/j.chb.2020.106395.